

Final Hydrology & Hydraulics Report

2023 Two Fish Passage Culvert Replacements

Old Tyonek 1 (ADF&G #20601535)

Unnamed Old Tyonek 2

Near Tyonek, Alaska

April 19, 2024

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

°F	degrees Fahrenheit
ADF&G	Alaska Department of Fish and Game
AEP	annual exceedance probability
AWC	Anadromous Waters Catalog
BFW	bankfull width
cfs	cubic feet per second
CMP	corrugated metal pipe
D100	maximum streambed material size
DEM	digital elevation model
ESRI	Environmental Systems Research Institute, Inc.
FPID	Fish Passage Inventory Database
fps	feet per second
ft	foot/feet
H&H	hydrology and hydraulics
HDR	HDR Engineering, Inc.
HW/D	headwater to diameter ratio
HY-8	HY-8 Culvert Hydraulic Analysis Program
ID	Identification
in.	inch(es)
KPB	Kenai Peninsula Borough
NAVD 88	North American Vertical Datum of 1988
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
NRCS	National Resources Conservation Service
PRISM	Parameter-elevation Regressions on Individual Slopes Model
SNAP	Scenarios Network for Alaska + Arctic Planning
TBC	The Boutet Company
TTCD	Tyonek Tribal Conservation District
TR-55	Technical Release 55
UAF	University of Alaska Fairbanks
USACE	U.S. Army Corps of Engineers
USDA	U.S. Department of Agriculture's
USGS	U.S. Geological Survey
VAP	vertical adjustment potential
Yr	Year(s)

1 Introduction and Objectives

The Tyonek Tribal Conservation District (TTCD) assists a number of communities along the northwest side of Cook Inlet with community-led conservation efforts. TTCD has secured funding through the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS) to replace two roadway crossings in Tyonek. These replacement projects aim to improve flood capacity, reconnect aquatic habitat, and provide fish passage.

The Boutet Company, Inc. (TBC) with the assistance of HDR Engineering, Inc. (HDR) has been contracted to guide the proposed roadway improvements and culvert replacements at the two sites. This hydrology and hydraulics (H&H) report describes the hydrology, existing conditions, and design of the two sites to:

- Evaluate watershed size, conveyance requirements, peak storm flows, floodplain issues, and scour analysis to meet hydrologic and fish passage requirements.
- Determine stream slope and profile for long-term channel stability and fish passage.
- Provide design guidance for the new crossing culvert width, invert elevations, length, structure type, and skew angle.
- Design stream substrate and other grade control structures.
- Provide minimum values of roadway grade, fill height, and width that correspond with the proposed culvert requirements.

1.1 Location

The Native Village of Tyonek resides on the northwest side of Cook Inlet, across from the Kenai Peninsula, and adjacent to the community of Beluga. The two sites are located on Airport Road and Tyonek Timber Road, near an old airstrip (oil and gas exploration), shown in Figure 1. These sites provide hydraulic connectivity for an unnamed tributary of Old Tyonek Creek.

Figure 1. Overview Map

1.2 Ownership

Tyonek resides within the Kenai Peninsula Borough’s (KPB) boundaries. The crossings, surrounding roads, and land are owned by the Tyonek Native Corporation (KPB 2024).

1.3 Design Criteria

The USFWS – Alaska’s Fish Passage Program Design Guidelines and the KPB Code of Ordinances were used as the design criteria for this project. The stricter USFWS guidelines state, “The structures will be sized to simulate the natural creek channel through the crossings, and to pass the 1 percent Annual Exceedance Probability (AEP) flood event at 80 percent the opening height of the culvert” (USFWS 2022).

The U.S. Federal Highway Administration’s HY-8 Culvert Hydraulic Analysis Program (HY-8), version 7.80.2, was used to model and analyze the existing and proposed crossings.

1.4 Flood Hazards or Floodplain Management Requirements

The sites are not located with a Federal Emergency Management Agency mapped floodplain and no additional local KPB management requirements exist; verified with the KPB floodplain administrator in March 2024. The crossings are located on a portion of Airport and Tyonek Timber Roads with moderate usage for the area.

1.5 Geotechnical

No geotechnical investigations were performed for this part of the project.

2 Site Visit

On September 14, 2023, HDR water resource engineer Irene Turletes, PE, and engineer-in-training Kacy Grundhauser accompanied TBC project staff to conduct a site visit to assess the two sites. The weather consisted of overcast skies with some light rain and temperatures in the mid-40's (degrees Fahrenheit). HDR assessed the existing crossing and took stream measurements, field notes, photos, and pebble counts at reference reaches. A reference reach is a non-crossing-impacted section of a stream that best describes the stream to aid in fish passage design. At each site, at least one reference reach was measured and recorded. Survey extents and reference reaches were delineated for survey. HDR's site visit notes are provided in Appendix A.

Both crossings provide connectivity for a northwestern, unnamed tributary of Old Tyonek Creek. The unnamed tributary crosses Airport Road near an old airstrip (oil and gas exploration), crosses Tyonek Timber Road, and then flows downstream to Q'at'l'u'hghulqet' Bena Lake draining to the main stem of Old Tyonek Creek. The main stem of Old Tyonek Creek then drains into Beshta Bay and into Cook Inlet.

Airport Road and Tyonek Timber Road are gravel roads that are approximately 24-feet wide and provide access for subsistence, recreation, and oil and gas exploration around the Native Village.

2.1 Old Tyonek 1

The Old Tyonek 1 conveys the first crossing of the unnamed tributary of Old Tyonek Creek under Airport Road flowing from west to east. This site was surveyed by Alaska Department of Fish and Game (ADF&G) in 2002 and 2016. In 2002, the crossing had a short perch at its outlet and a resident sculpin was observed in a downstream reach. In 2016, downstream beaver damming removed the previously observed downstream perch, but a grate had been added to the inlet, thought to prevent beavers from damming the culvert. Additionally, the site was backwatered and ponded upstream and downstream of the culvert.

During the 2023 TBC/HDR site visit, the grate over the inlet and any downstream perch were no longer present. However, the site was still ponded upstream and downstream of the culvert. Flow appeared to primarily come from the west with some accumulation from the northwest. Upstream of the existing crossing consists of many side channels that dead end or terminate in small pools. A main branch from the west appeared to be contributing the most flow and was chosen as the upstream reference reach. The upstream reference reach was located approximately 110-feet upstream of the crossing and had a measured bankfull width (BFW) of 4.5-feet wide and 2-feet deep. Downstream of the crossing, the channel makes a small, sharp turn to the northeast before winding its way to a marsh and pond. The downstream reference reach was located approximately 25-feet downstream of the crossing and had a measured BFW of 9-feet and a depth of 0.7-feet. A pebble count was taken at the downstream reference reach, resulting in an average sediment size of approximately ½inch.

The existing culvert is a noncorrugated, circular, metal pipe with a 20-inch diameter, 33-feet long, with a 2.18 percent slope. Compared to the upstream reference reach, the existing culvert had a

steeper slope with faster velocities. The pipe appeared to be in fair condition but is undersized for fish passage and the flows this crossing experiences. There was minimal cover over the pipe and some road rutting was visible, which may indicate the road has been overtopped in the past. Select site visit photographs are provided in Figure 2.

Roadway (facing north)

Inlet (facing northeast)

Inlet (facing downstream)

Upstream Reference Reach (facing downstream)

Downstream Channel and Pond (facing southeast)

Downstream Reference Reach (facing south)

Figure 2. Old Tyonek 1 Site Visit Photos

2.2 Old Tyonek 2

The Old Tyonek 2 conveys the second crossing of the unnamed tributary of Old Tyonek Creek under Tyonek Timber Road, flowing north to south. This crossing has not been surveyed by ADF&G. For reference, Old Tyonek 1's downstream marsh and pond outlets directly to Old Tyonek 2, shown in Figure 1.

During the 2023 TBC/HDR site visit, upstream flow was dispersed in the marsh with flow coming from the northeast. Flow passes through the crossing and a scour pool to riffle-pool-run sequences with woody grade control breaks and a gravel and cobble bottom. The downstream reference reach was located approximately 75-feet downstream of the crossing and had a measured BFW of 5-feet wide and 1.3-feet deep. A pebble count was taken at the downstream reference reach, resulting in an average sediment size of approximately 1.75-inches.

The existing culvert is a 48-inch diameter, corrugated metal pipe (CMP), 60-feet long, with a 2.68-percent slope. The pipe has a steep slope and was found to be in poor condition: the inlet crown is slightly smashed; there is a failure within the pipe shown in Figure 3; and near the outlet there are numerous erosion holes that flow drains out of before reaching the outlet. Below the outlet, there is embankment erosion and approximately a 1-foot perch into a scour pool that would likely impede fish passage. Sediment through the pipe consists of 6-inch cobbles that are assumed to have been part of original installation. Cover over the pipe was measured to be approximately 6-feet over the inlet and 8-feet over the outlet. Road prism erosion from surface runoff was visible on the downstream side. Some road rutting was visible, assumed to be from surface runoff from the east and west approaches. Select site visit photographs are provided in Figure 3.

Roadway (facing east)

Upstream Marsh (facing north)

Figure 3. Old Tyonek 2 Site Visit Photos

Culvert Inlet (facing southwest)

Within Culvert (facing downstream)

Within Culvert (facing upstream)

Downstream Reference Reach (facing south)

Figure 3 Continued. Old Tyonek 2 Site Visit Photos

2.3 Existing Site Summary

ADF&G site visit and general site information are summarized in Table 1. From the 2023 TBC/HDR site visit, existing culvert information is provided in Table 2 and reference reach measurements are provided in Table 3.

Table 1. General Site Information

Site	Road	Stream	ADF&G FPID	ADF&G Fish Passage Classification	Latitude Longitude
Old Tyonek 1	Airport Road	Unnamed Tributary of Old Tyonek Creek	20601535	Gray: may be inadequate for fish passage	61.06654°, -151.32612°
Old Tyonek 2	Tyonek Timber Road	Unnamed Tributary of Old Tyonek Creek	None	None	61.06517°, -151.32443°

Notes: ° = degree(s); ADF&G = Alaska Department of Fish and Game; CMP = corrugated metal pipe; FPID = Fish Passage Inventory Database; in. = inch(es).

Table 2. Existing Culverts

Site	Diameter Size (in.)	Type	Material	Slope (%)	Length (ft)
Old Tyonek 1	20	Noncorrugated Circular Pipe	Steel	-2.18	33
Old Tyonek 2	48	CMP	Steel	-2.68	60

Notes: % = percent; CMP = corrugated metal pipe; ft = foot/feet.; in. = inch(es).

Table 3. Reference Reach Information

Site	Length (ft)	Average Slope (%)	Bankfull Width (ft)	Bankfull Mean Depth (ft)	Floodplain Width (ft)	Location
Old Tyonek 1	33.5	-1.42	4.5	2.0	200+	Upstream of crossing
Old Tyonek 1	21	-5.83	9.0	0.7	200+	Downstream of crossing
Old Tyonek 2	35	-4.67	5.0	1.3	200+	Downstream of crossing

Notes: % = percent; ft = foot/feet.; in. = inch(es).

3 Hydrologic Analysis

Sites were analyzed hydraulically to calculate capacity of the proposed designs. Environmental Systems Research Institute, Inc. ArcGIS Pro, version 3.1.2, was used to visualize publicly available imagery and elevation data, with the project survey data. Drainage basins were delineated using ESRI world imagery and 1-foot contours, ranging in size from 0.53- to 0.56-acres. Drainage basins are shown in Figure 1 and their areas provided in Table 4.

To determine flood flow estimates, mean annual precipitation was determined using the 1971–2000 Parameter-elevation Regressions on Individual Slopes Model (PRISM) climate dataset for Alaska. While there are newer PRISM data sets available, the 1971–2000 data set is the one applicable to

the hydrologic analysis used. University of Alaska Fairbanks (UAF) Scenarios Network for Alaska + Arctic Planning (SNAP) Community Climate Charts estimates (UAF 2024) were also gathered.

Flood flow events are described by their chance of occurrence as a recurrence interval or as an AEP. A recurrence interval (or return period) is described as the average number of years between floods of a certain size and is based on the probability that the given event will be equaled or exceeded in any given year. An AEP is the percent chance of occurrence in any given year and is always provided as a fraction of one. The 2016 U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) regression equations were considered for estimation of flood flow estimates for various intervals (USGS 2016) and are provided below

3.1 2016 USGS Regression Equations

The 2016 USGS regression equations were developed to estimate flood magnitude and frequency for Alaska and conterminous basins in Canada using USGS annual peak flow data through water year 2012. The equations are valid for drainage basins between 0.4 and 1,000 square miles (256 to 640,000 acres); therefore, valid for the project's drainage basins. They use basin area and average mean annual precipitation to determine flood flow estimates. The 1971–2000 PRISM precipitation data was overlaid on the drainage basins and weighted precipitation average were calculated and are provided in Table 4.

To include climate change consideration, the 2016 USGS regressions equations were reran applying the SNAP Community Climate Charts data as an adjustment factor on average mean annual precipitation. SNAP Tyonek data for 2030 through 2099 suggests a 12.9 percent increase in precipitation over the design life of the structures (UAF 2023). Both PRISM only and SNAP-adjusted flood flow estimates were determined and are provided in Appendix B. Additionally, the nearby USGS station (Chuitna River USGS Station #15294450) was used as a reference to determine the reasonability of precipitation values.

The 2016 USGS regression equations with SNAP adjusted precipitation results were chosen as the design flood flow estimates, as they take into consideration increased flows over the design life of the structures. The design flood flow estimates for both proposed crossings are bolded in Table 4. Calculations used to determine project flood flow estimates are provided in Appendix B.

Table 4. Estimated Flood Flows for Proposed Crossings

Old Tyonek 1									
Basin Size (ac.)	339	% AEP / Recurrence-Interval Flood							
Method	Annual Mean Precip. (in.)	50%	20%	10%	4%	2%	1%	0.5%	0.2%
		2-Yr	5-Yr	10-Yr	25-Yr	50-Yr	100-Yr	200-Yr	500-Yr
2016 USGS Regression	30.9	19	34	48	66	81	98	116	141
2016 USGS SNAP Adjusted	34.8	21	39	53	73	90	108	127	154
Old Tyonek 2									
Basin Size (ac.)	369	% AEP / Recurrence-Interval Flood							
Method	Annual Mean Precip. (in.)	50%	20%	10%	4%	2%	1%	0.5%	0.2%
		2-Yr	5-Yr	10-Yr	25-Yr	50-Yr	100-Yr	200-Yr	500-Yr
2016 USGS Regression	30.8	20	37	51	71	87	105	123	150
2016 USGS SNAP Adjusted	34.8	22	41	56	78	95	115	135	163

Notes: % = percent; ac. = acres; AEP = Annual Exceedance Probability; in. = inch(es); Precip. = Precipitation; Yr = Year(s). Design flood flow estimates shown in **bold**.

4 Proposed Design

New crossings are proposed to accommodate the design flood flow event, improve fish passage, and improve floodplain connectivity. The existing crossings were initially perched and created impounded wetland area upstream of both crossings. The proposed designs will lower the inverts of the culverts to return the stream to its natural grade. It should be noted that the reference reaches taken during the site visit were not outside the influence of the existing culverts and will result in variability from them in the proposed slopes. The existing crossings were analyzed to determine the appropriate sizes for the proposed crossings.

4.1 Old Tyonek 1

The existing culvert was modeled as a 20-inch, noncorrugated metal pipe in HY-8. The analysis shows that the existing culvert would overtop the road at around 9.4 cfs or well below the 50 percent AEP (21 cfs). The existing condition HY-8 results can be found in Appendix C.

USFWS fish passage guidelines recommend accommodating at least the BFW (4.5-feet) and passing the 1 percent AEP (108 cfs) with a headwater to diameter ratio (HW/D) equal to or less than 80 percent. The proposed design includes one 108-inch, steel, round CMP, embedded further than the existing inlet thalweg to return the creek to its natural water surface elevation. Lines were plotted to analyze the existing channel’s vertical adjustment potential (VAP) to determine the proposed structure’s vertical location. The proposed culvert will be embedded with a low flow channel and thalweg set 3.6-feet above the pipe’s inverts, optimizing the full width of the pipe and meeting a substrate depth of at least 1.5 times the maximum substrate size (D100). Using a consistent embedment depth of 3.6-feet, HY-8 calculated the proposed culvert will pass the 1 percent AEP (108 cfs) at 59 percent full, with an inlet depth of 3.19-feet and an outlet velocity of 7.25 feet per second (fps). The proposed structure is estimated to pass 310 cfs before overtopping the road. Figure 4 shows the HY-8 inputs for the proposed conditions. Figure 5 shows the profile of the proposed

crossing during the 1 percent AEP and Table 5 provides results during various discharges. Table 6 provides the existing and proposed conditions for comparison.

Figure 4. Old Tyonek 1 – Proposed Conditions

Figure 5. Old Tyonek 1 – Proposed HY-8 Profile at 1 percent AEP

Table 5. Old Tyonek 1 – Proposed HY-8 Summary

Discharge Names	Total Discharge (cfs)	Culvert Discharge (cfs)	Headwater Elevation (ft)	Inlet Control Depth (ft)	Outlet Control Depth (ft)	Flow Type	Normal Depth (ft)	Critical Depth (ft)	Outlet Depth (ft)	Tailwater Depth (ft)	Outlet Velocity (fps)	Tailwater Velocity (fps)
50% AEP	21	21	249.25	0.92	1.19	3-M1t	0.92	0.56	1.20	1.20	2.0	2.0
20% AEP	39	39	249.74	1.52	1.68	3-M2t	1.36	0.85	1.33	1.33	3.3	2.5
10% AEP	53	53	250.08	1.93	2.02	3-M2t	1.66	1.03	1.41	1.41	4.2	2.9
4% AEP	73	73	250.53	2.44	2.47	3-M2t	2.05	1.28	1.52	1.52	5.4	3.2
2% AEP	90	90	250.89	2.83	2.83	3-M2t	2.36	1.47	1.59	1.59	6.3	3.5
1% AEP	108	108	251.26	3.19	3.20	3-M2t	2.68	1.66	1.67	1.67	7.3	3.8
0.5% AEP	127	127	251.62	3.54	3.56	2-M2c	3.03	1.84	1.84	1.75	7.8	4.0
0.2% AEP	154	154	252.12	4.01	4.06	2-M2c	3.53	2.09	2.09	1.85	8.3	4.3

Notes: cfs = cubic feet per second; fps = feet per second; ft = foot/feet. **Bold** indicates design criteria discharge.

Table 6. Old Tyonek 1 – Existing vs. Proposed Conditions

Condition	Diameter Size (in.)	Slope (%)	Length (ft)	Design Flow (cfs)	Outlet Depth at Design Flow (ft)	Outlet Velocity at Design Flow (fps)
Existing	20	-2.18	33	Overtopping = 8	0.83	8.7
Proposed	108	-0.5	68	1% AEP = 108	1.67	7.3

Notes: fps = feet per second, ft = foot/feet; in. = inch(es).

For stable streambed material at the 1 percent AEP, a D100 of 15 inches is recommended. A design streambed mix composed of 40 percent usable excavated existing streambed material with 60 percent Class I riprap is recommended. Figure 6 depicts the particle size distribution of the design mix compared to an idealized Fuller Thompson calculated gradation and the site visit's pebble count gradation taken at the downstream reference reach. While the pebble count provides a sediment size estimate, a design mix developed to confirm stability at the 1-percent AEP. Streambed material may need to be supplemented with alternatively sourced or barged in material to meet the recommended D100. Preliminary gradation calculations are provided in Appendix B and final gradations will be provided on the construction drawings.

Figure 6. Old Tyonek 1 – Sediment Gradation

The installation will consist of one 108-inch round CMP, located near the existing pipe’s alignment but skewed to the roadway to better align with the stream. To meet minimum cover and road grade requirements, the road profile was elevated, and fill is proposed to extend on the southeast side of the road. Inverts and thalweg elevations have been recommended based on VAP consideration and reasonable tie-in locations to the existing channel. While the proposed pipe’s slope differs from the reference reaches investigated in the field, the proposed design minimizes the length of stream requiring modification and uses the natural elevation change through the project area. A stream diversion will be required during the construction of the proposed culvert. Additionally, a small length of stream regrading will be needed at the upstream and downstream tie in locations to provide a smooth thalweg transition between the existing and reconstructed channel. The accompanying 95 percent Plan Set, developed by TBC, provides the plan view, profile view, details, and environmental plan (TBC 2024).

While not hydraulically necessary, the construction diversion culvert could be reused as a permanent overflow culvert. If implemented, the upstream invert of an overflow culvert should be located at least 1-foot above the thalweg invert of the main pipe to prevent channel migration at low flows. Further consideration may be warranted to determine if this is feasible at this site due to layout and construction phasing.

4.2 Old Tyonek 2

The existing culvert was modeled a 48-inch, noncorrugated metal pipe in HY-8. The analysis shows that the existing culvert would reach 80 percent around 101 cfs or at 88 percent of the 1 percent

AEP (115 cfs). The existing condition HY-8 model input and output graphic can be found in Appendix C.

USFWS fish passage guidelines recommend accommodating at least the BFW (5-feet) and passing the 1 percent AEP (115 cfs) with a headwater to diameter ratio (HW/D) equal to or less than 80 percent. The proposed design includes one 108-inch, steel, round CMP, embedded to return the creek to its natural water surface elevation. Lines were plotted to analyze the existing channel's VAP to determine the proposed structure's vertical location. The proposed culvert will be embedded with a low flow channel and thalweg set 3.6-feet above the pipe's inverts, optimizing the full width of the pipe and meeting a substrate depth of at least 1.5 times the maximum substrate size (D100). Using a consistent embedment depth of 3.6-feet, HY-8 calculated the proposed culvert will pass the 1 percent AEP (115 cfs) at 61-percent full, with an inlet depth of 3.28-feet and an outlet velocity of 7.48 fps. The proposed structure is estimated to pass 454 cfs before overtopping the road. Figure 7 shows the HY-8 inputs for the proposed conditions. Figure 8 shows the profile of the proposed crossing during the 1 percent AEP and Table 7 provides results during various discharges. Table 8 provides the existing and proposed conditions for comparison.

Figure 7. Old Tyonek 2 – Proposed Conditions

Figure 8. Old Tyonek 2 – Proposed HY-8 Profile at 1 percent AEP

Table 7. Old Tyonek 2 – Proposed HY-8 Summary

Discharge Names	Total Discharge (cfs)	Culvert Discharge (cfs)	Headwater Elevation (ft)	Inlet Control Depth (ft)	Outlet Control Depth (ft)	Flow Type	Normal Depth (ft)	Critical Depth (ft)	Outlet Depth (ft)	Tailwater Depth (ft)	Outlet Velocity (fps)	Tailwater Velocity (fps)
50% AEP	22	22	238.31	0.91	1.12	3-M1t	0.61	0.58	1.14	1.14	2.2	2.7
20% AEP	41	41	238.90	1.54	1.71	3-M1t	0.91	0.87	1.24	1.24	3.7	3.4
10% AEP	56	56	239.30	1.97	2.11	3-M1t	1.11	1.07	1.31	1.31	4.8	3.8
4% AEP	78	78	239.83	2.52	2.64	3-M1t	1.36	1.33	1.39	1.39	6.3	4.4
2% AEP	95	95	240.21	2.89	3.02	2-M2c	1.54	1.52	1.52	1.45	7.0	4.7
1% AEP	115	115	240.63	3.28	3.44	2-M2c	1.75	1.72	1.72	1.52	7.5	5.1
0.5% AEP	135	135	241.03	3.64	3.84	2-M2c	1.94	1.91	1.91	1.58	7.9	5.4
0.2% AEP	163	163	241.55	4.13	4.36	2-M2c	2.21	2.17	2.17	1.66	8.5	5.8

Notes: cfs = cubic feet per second; fps = feet per second; ft = foot/feet. **Bold** indicates design criteria discharge.

Table 8. Old Tyonek 2 – Existing vs. Proposed Conditions

Condition	Diameter Size (in.)	Slope (%)	Length (ft)	Design Flow (cfs)	Outlet Depth at Design Flow (ft)	Outlet Velocity at Design Flow (fps)
Existing	48	-2.68	60	1% AEP = 115	3.24	10.6
Proposed	108	-2.0	70	1% AEP = 115	1.72	7.5

Notes: fps = feet per second, ft = foot/feet; in. = inch(es).

For stable streambed material at the 1 percent AEP, a D100 of 16 inches is recommended. A design streambed mix composed of 40 percent usable excavated existing streambed material with 60 percent Class I riprap is recommended. Figure 9 depicts the particle size distribution of the design

mix compared to an idealized Fuller Thompson calculated gradation and the site visit’s pebble count gradation taken at the downstream reference reach. While the pebble count provides a sediment size estimate, a design mix was developed to confirm stability at the 1 percent AEP. Streambed material may need to be supplemented with alternatively sourced or barged in material to meet the recommended D100. Preliminary gradation calculations are provided in Appendix B and final gradations will be provided on the construction drawings.

Figure 9. Old Tyonek 2 – Sediment Gradation

The installation will consist of one 108-inch round CMP, located along the existing pipe’s alignment and perpendicular to the roadway. Inverts and thalweg elevations have been recommended based on VAP consideration and reasonable tie-in locations to the existing channel. A stream diversion will be required during the construction of the proposed culvert. Additionally, approximately 41-feet of stream regrading will be needed at the downstream tie in location to mitigate the existing perch and provide a smooth thalweg transition between the existing and reconstructed channel. The accompanying 95 percent Plan Set, developed by TBC, provides the plan view, profile view, details, and environmental plan (TBC 2024).

5 Summary

The Old Tyonek 1 and 2 designs meet the USFWS fish passage design guidelines by passing the 1 percent AEP flood event at 80 percent the opening height of the culvert. The installations will accommodate normal sediment transport, and the use of the existing downstream channels will

relieve the project of extensive channel reconstruction. The proposed crossings are summarized in Table 9. Additional construction details such as detailed inverts, slopes, thalweg elevations, and substrate design parameters will be incorporated into the construction drawings produced by TBC.

Table 9. Proposed Crossing Summary Table

Site	Basin Size (ac.)	Design Discharge (cfs)	Reference Reach		Existing Pipe			Proposed			
			BFW (ft)	Average Slope (%)	Size and Shape	Slope (%)	Length (ft)	Size and Shape	Length (ft)	Slope (%)	D100 (in.)
Old Tyonek 1	339	108	4.5	-1.42 / -5.83	20-in. Noncorrugated Circular Pipe	-2.18	33	108-inch Steel Circular Pipe	68	-0.5	15
Old Tyonek 2	369	115	5.0	-4.67	48-in. CMP	-2.68	60	108-inch Steel Circular Pipe	70	-2.0	16

Notes: % = percent; ac. = acres; BFW = bankfull width; CMP = corrugated metal pipe; cfs = cubic feet per second; ft = foot/feet.; in. = inch(es).

6 References

- ADF&G Alaska Department of Fish and Game
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Appendix A – HDR Field Notes

Date: 9 / 14 / 2023	Field Team: I. Turletas, K. Gundhauser
Start Time: 10:30	Weather: light rain / overcast.
End Time: 12:05	Site Observers: TBC, Tim, Shawn, Jason

Site Information:

Site ID: Tyonek 1535	Roadway: Tyonek Timber Rd.
Waterway: Unnamed	Dir. of Flow: Southeast
ADF&G #: 20601535	GPS Waypoint No.: Yes, see inreach.

Existing Culvert: water depth (inlet) = 7"

No. of Barrels: 1 Rust Line Height: 3", 15" wide Barrel Slope: Mild / Steep / —
 Skew (0° = perp. to road): 0° Cover (approx.): US ~6", minimal. DS ~6", minimal

Barrel Shape: Circular Box Elliptical Pipe Arch Arch Open Bottom
 Diameter: 20 in Span: — x Rise: —

Pipe Material: Metal - Steel Concrete/RCP - Corrugated Plastic - Smooth Plastic - Timber - Masonry

Performance Problems

Debris/Veg Blockage *Some grasses but no blockage.*

Buoyancy or Crushing Related Inlet Failure *None, steel.*

Poor Channel Alignment *Could potentially angle culvert but @ low point in road.*

Previous/Frequent Overtopping *Some signs outlet SE side.*

Local Outlet Scour *no, pond & riffle.*

Embankment Piping *None.*

Channel Degradation / Headcut *no.*

No Access / Buried / Submerged *No.*

Roadway Erosion *Some, see overtopping.*

Utilities Present *None.*

Photographs:

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Inlet	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Outlet	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Rdwy (ahead)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Rdwy (back)
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> View Upstream	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> View Downstream	Other: _____	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> US Ref Reach	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DS Ref Reach		

US water 12' 12-18"

		Width	Depth	Vegetation
US	OWH	3' - 4'	19"	mud, green mossy sedge
	BFW	4.5'	+6-9' 24"	Grasses, Alders, birch, spruce
	Floodplain	200+	—	Birch, Spruces Alder, willows
DS	OWH	4.5'	3"	Horsetail
	BFW	9'	8"	Grasses,
	Floodplain	wide	—	Alder, dead spruce, dead Alder? 1

Notes:

inlet slightly perched, water is 11" deep in front of inlet.
 US - lots of side channels that dead end or are small ponds.

Recommend - raise road, align culvert angled DS to better fit stream.

Upstream Reference Reach: DS of Alder channel & US of side channel/pond.
Location & Description: see inreach point for DS point of Ref reach

Downstream Reference Reach:

Just
 Riffle [^] ds of culvert.

Location & Description:

Plan View Sketch

Cross Section Sketch

Pebble Count		Riffe
Size	Count	
mud/silt		
< 2		
2		
2.8		
4		
5.6		
8		
11		
16		
22.6		
32		
32 45		
64		
90		
128		
180		
> 180		

Site sketch

Date: 9 / 14 / 2023	Field Team: I. Turletes, K. Grundhauser
Start Time: 12:45	Weather: overcast
End Time: 13:50	Site Observers: Tim, Shawn, Jason.

Site Information:

Site ID: Unnamed, DS of 20601535	Roadway: Tyonek Timber Rd.
Waterway: Unnamed	Dir. of Flow: South
ADF&G #: No ID/site.	GPS Waypoint No.: in reach.

Existing Culvert: -very poor condition / water 8" deep, 34" wide, 12-16" water depth in front of culvert

No. of Barrels: 1 Rust Line Height: 16" ^{noted: through} Barrel Slope: Mild / Steep / _____

Skew (0° = perp. to road): Slight skew Cover (approx.): US ^{6' below} 6' DS 3'

Barrel Shape: Circular Box Elliptical Pipe Arch Arch Open Bottom

Diameter: 48" Span: _____ x Rise: _____

Pipe Material: Metal - Concrete/RCP - Corrugated Plastic - Smooth Plastic - Timber - Masonry

corrugated, collapsing top & bottom inlet.

Performance Problems

Debris/Veg Blockage *none blockage*

Buoyancy or Crushing Related Inlet Failure *- debris crushing @ inlet top.*

Poor Channel Alignment *Good*

Previous/Frequent Overtopping *none.*

Local Outlet Scour *Pool*

Embankment Piping *none*

Channel Degradation / Headcut *none.*

No Access / Buried / Submerged *none.*

Roadway Erosion *potholes.*

Utilities Present *none*

Photographs:

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Inlet	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Outlet	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Rdwy (ahead)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Rdwy (back)
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> View Upstream	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> View Downstream	Other: _____	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> US Ref Reach	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DS Ref Reach	<i>Crossing is slightly west of rdwy low point</i>	

		Width	Depth	Vegetation
US	OWH	/	/	Sedges, wetlands
	BFW	/	/	alder, willow
	Floodplain	+200'	-	Birch, Spruce
DS	OWH	3.5'	5" water / 10"	Pool Grasses;
	BFW	4.5'	16"	Willow Alder
	Floodplain	+200'	-	Birch, Spruce.

Notes:

inlet - hole in top of pipe ~ 5ft in.

6" cobbles in pipe.

water coming out of hole in bottom of pipe, slight seepage ~ 1 ft.

Upstream Reference Reach: No ref reach, US in pond.
Location & Description:

Pebble Count	
Size	Count
mud/silt	—
< 2	
2	
2.8	
4	
5.6	
8	
11	
16	
22.6	
32	
34 45	
64	
90	
128	
180	
> 180	

Site ID: Unnamed, DS of 20601535

Downstream Reference Reach: DS of DS pond, before pool & steps.

Location & Description: pools & steps DS, slightly steeper

Pebble Count	
Size	Count
mud/silt	
< 2	
2	
2.8	
4	I
5.6	II
8	III
11	II
16	IIII I
22.6	IIII
32	IIII IIII
45	IIII
64	IIII IIII
90	IIII III
128	IIII IIII
180	I
> 180	

14 Sept 2023 Tyonek Site Visit

Field crew: I. Tulekas, K. Gundhauer

TBC: Tim Alley, Shawn (EIT), Jason (Survey)

(Also saw David Kyoto w/ Tyonek Native Corp.)

9:00 @ Spernak's

9:20 Depart Anchorage, light rain.

9:50 Arrived in Tyonek. Took SUV & truck, overcast.

10:30 - 12:05 Onsite @ 20601535.

12:45 - 13:50 onsite @ site DS of 20601535. No ADF86 site ID, just around the intersection corner.

14:00. Looked @ 20601534, upper Tyonek w/ two large (~9') culverts. Culverts appear to be in good condition, slightly higher water than last time we visited (2022). ADF86 fish pass rating is green. Further conversation on cost to benefit ratio @ this site.

14:20 looked @ 20601540 lower Tyonek site. Lots of drift wood below ^{existing} overflow culverts. Tim mentioned potentially armoring ds side slope from inlet. Wet overflow area. DS outlet scour pool appears wider/larger. US has less debris blocking inlet of pipe. Inlet still damaged but not much worse than last time. Debris on US side slope, should clean up during construction. Reminds that there is a lot of water @ this site.

16:00 Depart Tyonek.

16:30 Arrived in Anc.

17:00 Returned home.

Appendix B – Supplemental Calculations

Appendix B: Supplemental Calculations

Project Name: 2023 Two Crossings - Old Tyonek Creek

Updated: 12/12/23 W. Najjar

Step 1: Use basin size (ft²) to determine which peak flow calculation methods apply by basin size.

Basin #	Basin Size	Basin Size	Basin Size	Applicable Method
	ft ²	acres	mi ²	
Old Tyonek Creek 1 (20601535)	14,754,705	339	0.529	2016 USGS Regression Equations
Old Tyonek Creek 2	16,080,381	369	0.577	2016 USGS Regression Equations

Basin falls within 2016 USGS Regression Equation parameters

Basin falls only within NRCS TR-55 Parameters

Basin falls within Rational Method parameters and NRCS TR-55 parameters

2016 USGS Regression Equations					% Exceedance							
Basin ID	Basin Size	Basin Size	PRISM Precip *	PRISM Precip	50%	20%	10%	4%	2%	1%	0.5%	0.2%
	ft ²	mi ²	mm *100	in	2-year	5-year	10-year	25-year	50-year	100-year	200-year	500-year
Old Tyonek Creek 1 (20601535)	14,754,705	0.53	78,403	30.9	19	34	48	66	81	98	116	141
Old Tyonek Creek 2	16,080,381	0.58	78,280	30.8	20	37	51	71	87	105	123	150

*Values calculated in GIS using Zonal Statistics tool with basin polygons and 1 m by 1 m resampled rainfall raster.

Source: Mean Precipitation for Alaska 1971-2000

**See SNAP Data

Basin falls within 2016 Regression Equation parameters
Basin falls outside of 2016 USGS Regression Equations

Basin ID	Basin Size	SNAP** Adjusted PRISM Precip	% Exceedance							
			50%	20%	10%	4%	2%	1%	0.5%	0.2%
	mi ²	in	2-year	5-year	10-year	25-year	50-year	100-year	200-year	500-year
Old Tyonek Creek 1 (20601535)	0.53	34.8	21	39	53	73	90	108	127	154
Old Tyonek Creek 2	0.58	34.8	22	41	56	78	95	115	135	163

Local Stream Gage Factors

Map Identification No.	USGS Station No.	USGS station Name	Annual exceedance probability discharge, in cubic feet per second												Skew coefficient used for Sta AEP	Skew coefficient used in appendix B	MSE of skew coefficient used in appendix B
			50-percent			20-percent			10-percent			4-percent					
			Sta	Reg	Wtd	Sta	Reg	Wtd	Sta	Reg	Wtd	Sta	Reg	Wtd			
194	15294450	Chuitna River near Tyonek, Alaska	3,260	2,560	3,210	5,360	3,670	5,040	8,290	4,470	7,210	15,400	5,500	10,600	2.740	--	--

Map Identification No.	USGS Station No.	USGS station Name	Annual exceedance probability discharge, in cubic feet per second												Skew coefficient used for Sta AEP	Skew coefficient used in appendix B	MSE of skew coefficient used in appendix B
			2-percent			1-percent			0.5-percent			0.2-percent					
			Sta	Reg	Wtd	Sta	Reg	Wtd	Sta	Reg	Wtd	Sta	Reg	Wtd			
194	15294450	Chuitna River near Tyonek, Alaska	24,900	6,270	12,800	40,800	7,050	14,300	67,500	7,830	15,200	132,000	8,910	16,100	2.74	--	--

[Location of map identification Nos. are shown in figure 1. Usage in this report: Regr, used to develop regression equations; RegISkew, used to develop regional skew; redundant, omitted from any regional analysis on the basis of hydrologic redundancy with another site; Sta, used for station analysis

Map identification No.	USGS station No.	Station name	Drainage area (mi ²)	Mean annual precipitation (in.)	Kendall tau correlation coefficient, for sites having statistically significant trends	Kendall tau p-value	Usage in this report	Skew Region, for sites within applicable range of drainage area	Period of record used	Historic period length (years) ¹	Water year(s) for data omitted from analysis ²	Number of peaks in record ³	Perception threshold for water years noted (ft ³ /s) ^{4,5}	Interval discharge range for noted water year (ft ³ /s) ⁵	PILF threshold (ft ³ /s) ⁶	Number of PILFs
194	15294450	Chuitna River near Tyonek, Alaska	132	42	--	--	Regr	--	1976-1987	12		12	1987: 0-10,000 (o, t)	1987: 10,000-INF (t)	10.0x	0

Appendix B: Supplemental Calculations

SNAP** Data

Tyonek, AK

Month	Precipitation (in)				2030-2099 % Increase
	Historical	2030-2039	2060-2069	2090-2099	
January	1.77	2.17	2.40	2.24	3.6
February	1.30	1.65	1.61	1.61	-2.4
March	1.14	1.50	1.50	1.54	2.6
April	1.18	1.18	1.54	1.34	13.3
May	1.22	1.42	1.34	1.46	2.8
June	1.50	1.42	1.77	1.81	27.8
July	1.97	1.81	2.20	2.36	30.4
August	3.15	3.35	3.39	4.02	20.0
September	3.94	4.02	3.78	4.72	17.6
October	3.23	3.39	3.58	3.66	8.1
November	2.40	2.52	2.99	2.68	6.3
December	2.52	2.76	3.07	3.23	17.1
Annual	25.31	27.17	29.17	30.67	12.9
			7.4	12.9	

Decimal Increase: 1.129

Average Monthly Precipitation for Tyonek (Qaggeyshlat), Alaska
Historical PRISM and 5-Model Projected Average at 2km resolution, Medium Emissions (RCP 6.0) Scenario

SNAP data collected from UAF Scenarios Network for Alaska + Arctic Planning website:

Data: <https://www.snap.uaf.edu/tools/community-charts>

About: <https://uaf-snap.org/snap-story/community-charts-help-northerners-see-changes/>

Stream Bed Sizing - Old Tyonek 1

Updated 04/04/2024 K. Grundhauser

Inputs Set by Specs Calculated

Step 1 From HEC-RAS or HY-8 enter values for depth and velocity of Q100 flows and select D85/15 and stability coefficients

This will produce the coarse fraction gradations for rip rap sizing at the bottom of the table

Using Corps of Engineers Equations - FHWA Circular on Development in the River System - Page 6.25.

FHWA NHI 01-004; River Engineering for Highway Encroachments, 2001
http://www.fhwa.dot.gov/engineering/hydraulics/library_arc.cfm?pub_number=8&id=20

Safety Factor	1.5		
Failure	0.3	Angular Rock?	Angular angular rock)
Vertical Velocity Distribution Coeff	1.00	(1.0 for straight channels)	
Blanket Thickness Coeff	1	(1xD100 or 1.5 or D50 max, whichever is greater)	
Local depth of flow	1.67	ft for 100-year event	
Unit Weight of water	62.4	lb/ft ³ (assumed)	
Unit weight of rock	165	lb/ft ³ (assumed)	
Local depth-average velocity	7.25	ft/s from 100-year event avg. velocity in pipe	
Side Slope correction factor	1		
Gravitational Acceleration	32.2	ft/s ²	
D85/D15	3.4	(1.7-5.2) IN RANGE	
D50/D30	2		

Note: This method is based on the minimum D30 size

Riprap Design Method - Selecting Proper Gradation, Page 131.

Design Hydrology and Sedimentology for Small Catchments, Haan, Barfield and Hayes, 1981.

D15	0.3	ft	4.0	inches
D30	0.4	ft	5.0	inches
D50	0.6	ft	8.0	inches
D85	1.0	ft	13.0	inches
D100	1.2	ft	15.0	inches

Using D50 size, used FHWA circular for Rip Rap design to spec out D100, D85 and D15.
 D100 = 2.0D50

Step 2 Calculate Fuller Thompson Gradation of fine fraction,

Fuller-Thompson Estimating for Maximum Density:
 Method Adapted from US Forest Service Stream Simulation Guidelines

			Fuller Thompson Power n	0.5
			D15 copied from Step 1	4.0
			Particle Size	
	d	d	Sieve	% passing
	Inches	mm		
	12.0000	304.8	12	100.0%
	10.0000	254	10	100.0%
	2.0000	50.8	2	70.7%
	1.5000	38.1	1.5	61.2%
	1.0000	25.4	1	50.0%
	0.7500	19.05	0.75	43.3%
	0.5000	12.7	0.5	35.4%
	0.1870	4.75	#4	21.6%
	0.0787	2.00	#10	14.0%
	0.0167	0.425	#40	6.5%
	0.0059	0.15	#100	3.8%
	0.0030	0.075	#200	2.7%

Particle Size	Particle Size (in.)	Tot #	Item %	% Cum
0.062	0.0024	0	0%	0%
0.125	0.0049	0	0%	0%
0.25	0.0098	0	0%	0%
0.5	0.0197	0	0%	0%
1	0.039	0	0%	0%
2.8	0.110	0	0%	0%
4	0.157	1	2%	2%
5.6	0.220	2	3%	5%
8	0.315	4	7%	12%
11.3	0.445	2	3%	15%
16	0.630	6	10%	25%
22.6	0.890	3	5%	30%
32	1.26	9	15%	45%
45	1.77	5	8%	53%
64	2.52	9	15%	68%
90	3.54	8	13%	82%
128	5.04	10	17%	98%
180	7.09	1	2%	100%
256	10.08	0	0%	100%
362	14.25	0	0%	100%
512	20.16	0	0%	100%
1024	40.31	0	0%	100%
2048	80.63	0	0%	100%
3000	118.11	0	0%	100%
SUM		60	100%	100%

Step 3 Select mix of coarse and fine materials for final gradation. Use standard Rip Rap or spec special rip rap, use fines calculated in Step 2 or use standard aggregate specs.

Compare to Fuller-Thompson Estimating for Maximum Density:
 Method Adapted from US Forest Service Stream Simulation Guidelines
 D30 6.0 Stability (D30) Good
 D30 Req'd 5.0

Selected Mix Proportions %	COARSE MATERIAL					FINE MATERIAL		Combined Gradation %	Fuller Thomp, Gradation calc from D100 in Step 1
	Custom Rip Rap mix	Type IV Rip Rap	Type III Rip Rap	Type II Rip Rap	Type I Rip Rap	Coarse Fraction	Based on Tyonek local gravel		
	0	0	0	0.00	0.60	0.6000	0.40	1.0000	

Gradation Tables for Components										
Size (inches)	Sieve Size	% Passing								
54	54"		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
48	48"		90%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
34	34"		50%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
30	30"		35%	90%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
24	24"		25%	50%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
20	20"		15%	15%	90%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
16	16"		0%	0%	50%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
12	12"		0%	0%	15%	100%	100%	100%	100%	89.4%
10	10"		0%	0%	0%	90%	90%	100%	94%	81.6%
8	8"		0%	0%	0%	50%	50%	100%	70%	73.0%
5	5"		0%	0%	0%	20%	20%	100%	52%	57.7%
3	3"		0%	0%	0%	10%	10%	100%	46%	44.7%
2	2"		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	82.0%	33%	36.5%
1.5	1.5"		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	71.0%	28%	31.6%
1	1"	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	58.0%	23%	25.8%
0.75	0.75"	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	50.0%	20%	22.4%
0.5	0.5"	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	41.0%	16%	18.3%
0.187	#4	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	25.0%	10%	11.2%
0.0787	#10	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	16.0%	6%	7.2%
0.0167	#40	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	7.0%	3%	3.3%
0.0059	#100	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	4.0%	2%	2.0%
0.0030	#200	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	3.0%	1%	1.4%

Design Fuller-Thompson

Step 4 Compare to ideal Fuller Thompson Gradation and adjust components if necessary, this graph created from tables in Step 3, Design and Fuller-Thompson

Gradation values should be within +/-5% of this gradation (Rice) AND we need to have at least 5% sand size (#10) or smaller (Forest Service) in the combined gradation

Stream Bed Sizing - Old Tyonek 2

Updated 03/05/2024 K. Grundhauser

Inputs Set by Specs Calculated

Step 1 From HEC-RAS or HY-8 enter values for depth and velocity of Q100 flows and select D85/15 and stability coefficients

This will produce the coarse fraction gradations for rip rap sizing at the bottom of the table

Using Corps of Engineers Equations - FHWA Circular on Development in the River System - Page 6.25.

FHWA NHI 01-004; River Engineering for Highway Encroachments, 2001
http://www.fhwa.dot.gov/engineering/hydraulics/library_arc.cfm?pub_number=8&id=20

Safety Factor	1.5		
Failure	0.3	Angular Rock?	Angular angular rock)
Vertical Velocity Distribution Coeff	1.00	(1.0 for straight channels)	
Blanket Thickness Coeff	1	(1xD100 or 1.5 or D50 max, whichever is greater)	
Local depth of flow	1.72	ft for 100-year event	
Unit Weight of water	62.4	lb/ft ³ (assumed)	
Unit weight of rock	165	lb/ft ³ (assumed)	
Local depth-average velocity	7.48	ft/s from 100-year event avg. velocity in pipe	
Side Slope correction factor	1		
Gravitational Acceleration	32.2	ft/s ²	
D85/D15	3.4	(1.7-5.2) IN RANGE	
D50/D30	2		

Note: This method is based on the minimum D30 size

Riprap Design Method - Selecting Proper Gradation, Page 131.

Design Hydrology and Sedimentology for Small Catchments, Haan, Barfield and Hayes, 1981.

D15	0.3	ft	4.0	inches
D30	0.4	ft	6.0	inches
D50	0.6	ft	8.0	inches
D85	1.1	ft	13.0	inches
D100	1.3	ft	16.0	inches

Using D50 size, used FHWA circular for Rip Rap design to spec out D100, D85 and D15.
 D100 = 2.0D50

Step 2 Calculate Fuller Thompson Gradation of fine fraction,

Fuller-Thompson Estimating for Maximum Density:
 Method Adapted from US Forest Service Stream Simulation Guidelines

Fuller Thompson Power n 0.5
 D15 copied from Step 1 4.0

d Inches	d mm	Particle Size Sieve	% passing
12.0000	304.8	12	100.0%
10.0000	254	10	100.0%
2.0000	50.8	2	70.7%
1.5000	38.1	1.5	61.2%
1.0000	25.4	1	50.0%
0.7500	19.05	0.75	43.3%
0.5000	12.7	0.5	35.4%
0.1870	4.75	#4	21.6%
0.0787	2.00	#10	14.0%
0.0167	0.425	#40	6.5%
0.0059	0.15	#100	3.8%
0.0030	0.075	#200	2.7%

Pebble Count					
Particle Size	Particle Size (in.)	Tot #	Item %	% Cum	
0.062	0.0024	0	0%	0%	0%
0.125	0.0049	0	0%	0%	0%
0.25	0.0098	0	0%	0%	0%
0.5	0.0197	0	0%	0%	0%
1	0.039	0	0%	0%	0%
2.8	0.110	0	0%	0%	0%
4	0.157	1	2%	2%	2%
5.6	0.220	2	3%	5%	5%
8	0.315	4	7%	12%	12%
11.3	0.445	2	3%	15%	15%
16	0.630	6	10%	25%	25%
22.6	0.890	3	5%	30%	30%
32	1.26	9	15%	45%	45%
45	1.77	5	8%	53%	53%
64	2.52	9	15%	68%	68%
90	3.54	8	13%	82%	82%
128	5.04	10	17%	98%	98%
180	7.09	1	2%	100%	100%
256	10.08	0	0%	100%	100%
362	14.25	0	0%	100%	100%
512	20.16	0	0%	100%	100%
1024	40.31	0	0%	100%	100%
2048	80.63	0	0%	100%	100%
3000	118.11	0	0%	100%	100%
SUM		60	100%	100%	100%

Step 3 Select mix of coarse and fine materials for final gradation. Use standard Rip Rap or spec special rip rap, use fines calculated in Step 2 or use standard aggregate specs.

Compare to Fuller-Thompson Estimating for Maximum Density:
 Method Adapted from US Forest Service Stream Simulation Guidelines
 D30 6.0 Stability (D30) Good
 D30 Req'd 6.0

Selected Mix Proportions %	COARSE MATERIAL					FINE MATERIAL		Combined Gradation %	Fuller Thomp, Gradation calc from D100 in Step 1
	Custom Rip Rap mix	Type IV Rip Rap	Type III Rip Rap	Type II Rip Rap	Type I Rip Rap	Coarse Fraction	Based on Tyonek local gravel		
	0	0	0	0.00	0.60	0.6000	0.40	1.0000	

Gradation Tables for Components										
Size (inches)	Sieve Size	% Passing								
54	54"		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
48	48"		90%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
34	34"		50%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
30	30"		35%	90%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
24	24"		25%	50%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
20	20"		15%	15%	90%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
16	16"		0%	0%	50%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
12	12"		0%	0%	15%	100%	100%	100%	100%	86.6%
10	10"		0%	0%	0%	90%	90%	100%	94%	79.1%
8	8"		0%	0%	0%	50%	50%	100%	70%	70.7%
5	5"		0%	0%	0%	20%	20%	100%	52%	55.9%
3	3"		0%	0%	0%	10%	10%	100%	46%	43.3%
2	2"		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	82.0%	33%	35.4%
1.5	1.5"		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	71.0%	28%	30.6%
1	1"	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	58.0%	23%	25.0%
0.75	0.75"	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	50.0%	20%	21.7%
0.5	0.5"	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	41.0%	16%	17.7%
0.187	#4	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	25.0%	10%	10.8%
0.0787	#10	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	16.0%	6%	7.0%
0.0167	#40	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	7.0%	3%	3.2%
0.0059	#100	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	4.0%	2%	1.9%
0.0030	#200	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	3.0%	1%	1.4%

Design Fuller-Thompson

Step 4 Compare to ideal Fuller Thompson Gradation and adjust components if necessary, this graph created from tables in Step 3, Design and Fuller-Thompson

Gradation values should be within +/-5% of this gradation (Rice) AND we need to have at least 5% sand size (#10) or smaller (Forest Service) in the combined gradation

Step 5

Weight (lbs)	RADIUS (ft)	DIA (IN)
1	0.11	2.7
25	0.33	8.0
30	0.35	8.5
40	0.39	9.3
45	0.40	9.7
50	0.42	10.1
75	0.48	11.5
100	0.53	12.7
150	0.60	14.5
200	0.67	16.0
300	0.76	18.3
400	0.84	20.1
500	0.90	21.7
700	1.01	24.2
800	1.06	25.3
1000	1.14	27.3
1400	1.27	30.5
1500	1.30	31.2
2000	1.43	34.4
2300	1.50	36.0
4000	1.81	43.3
5400	2.00	47.9
6000	2.07	49.6
7800	2.26	54.1

Riprap by Weight (lbs) Spec. Gravity =

2.6

(calculation assumes sphere)

Unit Weight=

162.24 pcf

AK DOT RIP Specification:

- Class I 0-50% weighing up to 25 pounds = 8"
0-10% weighing more than 50 pounds = 10"
- Class II 50-100% weighing 200 pounds or more = 16"
0-15% weighing up to 25 pounds = 8"
0-10% weighing more than 400 pounds = 20"
- Class III 50-100% weighing 700 pounds or more = 24"
0-15% weighing up to 25 pounds = 8"
0-10% weighing more than 1400 pounds = 30"
- Class IV 50-100% weighing 2000 pounds or more = 34"
0-15% weighing up to 400 pounds = 20"
0-10% weighing more than 5400 pounds = 48"

Anchorage Sand and Gravel Rip Rap Sizes from the website*

- Rip Rap Class I is approx. 1" to 12" in diameter.
Each piece weighs approx. 1 to 75 lbs. = 3"-12"
- Rip Rap Class II is approx. 15" to 21" in diameter.
Each piece weighs approx. 200 to 800 lbs. = 16"-25"
- Rip Rap Class III is approx. 21" to 30" in diameter.
Each piece weighs approx. 800 to 2,300 lbs. = 25"-36"
- Rip Rap Class IV is approx. 33" to 45" in diameter.
Each piece weighs approx. 2,300 to 7,800 lbs. = 36"-54"
- *Sieve sizes reported don't match calculated diameter.

Appendix C – Existing Condition HY-8 Analysis

Crossing Data - Exist Old Tyonek Creek 1

Crossing Properties
Name: Exist Old Tyonek Creek 1

Parameter	Value	Units
DISCHARGE DATA		
Discharge Method	Minimum, Design, and Maximum	
Minimum Flow	20.000	cfs
Design Flow	105.000	cfs
Maximum Flow	105.000	cfs
TAILWATER DATA		
Channel Type	Trapezoidal Channel	
Bottom Width	5.000	ft
Side Slope (H:V)	2.000	_:1
Channel Slope	0.0145	ft/ft
Manning's n (channel)	0.035	
Channel Invert Elevation	249.110	ft
Rating Curve	View...	
ROADWAY DATA		
Roadway Profile Shape	Constant Roadway Elevation	
First Roadway Station	0.000	ft
Crest Length	100.000	ft
Crest Elevation	251.900	ft
Roadway Surface	Gravel	
Top Width	20.000	ft

Culvert Properties

Existing Culvert

Add Culvert
Duplicate Culvert
Delete Culvert

Parameter	Value	Units
CULVERT DATA		
Name	Existing Culvert	
Shape	Circular	
Material	Corrugated Steel	
Diameter	1.667	ft
Embedment Depth	0.000	in
Manning's n	0.012	
Culvert Type	Straight	
Inlet Configuration	Thin Edge Projecting (Ke=0.9)	
Inlet Depression?	No	
SITE DATA		
Site Data Input Option	Culvert Invert Data	
Inlet Station	0.000	ft
Inlet Elevation	249.830	ft
Outlet Station	33.000	ft
Outlet Elevation	249.110	ft
Number of Barrels	1	
Computed Culvert Slope	0.021818	ft/ft

Old Tyonek 1 – Existing Conditions

Crossing Data - Exist Old Tyonek Creek 2

Crossing Properties
 Name:

Parameter	Value	Units
DISCHARGE DATA		
Discharge Method	Minimum, Design, and Maximum	
Minimum Flow	22.000	cfs
Design Flow	101.000	cfs
Maximum Flow	115.000	cfs
TAILWATER DATA		
Channel Type	Trapezoidal Channel	
Bottom Width	2.000	ft
Side Slope (H:V)	2.000	_:1
Channel Slope	0.0462	ft/ft
Manning's n (channel)	0.035	
Channel Invert Elevation	235.740	ft
Rating Curve	View...	
ROADWAY DATA		
Roadway Profile Shape	Constant Roadway Elevation	
First Roadway Station	0.000	ft
Crest Length	100.000	ft
Crest Elevation	249.230	ft
Roadway Surface	Gravel	
Top Width	20.000	ft

Culvert Properties
 Existing Culvert

[Add Culvert](#)

[Duplicate Culvert](#)

[Delete Culvert](#)

Parameter	Value	Units
CULVERT DATA		
Name	Existing Culvert	
Shape	Circular	
Material	Corrugated Aluminum	
Diameter	4.000	ft
Embedment Depth	0.000	in
Manning's n	0.031	
Culvert Type	Straight	
Inlet Configuration	Thin Edge Projecting (Ke=0.9)	
Inlet Depression?	No	
SITE DATA		
Site Data Input Option	Culvert Invert Data	
Inlet Station	0.000	ft
Inlet Elevation	238.580	ft
Outlet Station	60.000	ft
Outlet Elevation	236.970	ft
Number of Barrels	1	
Computed Culvert Slope	0.026833	ft/ft

Old Tyonek 2 – Existing Conditions